

8T – Inclusion Arrows

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present a way to think about the idea of a universe packet using inclusion arrows. Each new manifold is a part of the subset of sub-manifolds generated by the original manifold.

Using such an idea allows us to provide a possible answer to the question of what was there before the beginning.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \tag{1.48}$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \tag{1.49}$$

The idea of inclusion arrows can fit the features of manifold creation. That is each new manifold is an embedded space of the original manifold, each manifold is the domain of a set of manifolds embedding's which rose from the original manifold. Define the inclusion arrow as:

$$l: S_0 \rightarrow S_{n+1}$$

One will require the inclusion map of the 8T to possess the homomorphism trait. Such is required to ensure that the new sub-manifold will preserve the same features and structure of the original manifold. I.e. to be a complete manifold, which is simply connected and possess (3,1) signature. For that purpose the heredity condition was presented:

$$\zeta: S_0^{(3,1)} \rightarrow S_{n+1}^{(3,1)}$$

In contrast to the idea of universe packet as presented in the 8T thesis, this idea emphasize of sub-structure within larger structures. Those substructures are than yielding from them sub-manifolds and the process than goes endlessly. The idea can be simply expressed using functors and sets.

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi: Top &\rightarrow Set \\ span(s_0) &= \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^K S_{n+1} \mid n \in \mathbb{R}, K \in \mathbb{R} \right\} . \\ \sum_{n=1}^K S_{n+1} &\subset S_0 \end{aligned}$$

Using that idea it is possible to provide a possible answer to the question of what was before the beginning. The answer using that idea, is that there was another manifold which had a unique time arrow. Time existed before singularity, it existed on the spanning space of our own manifold, when an own manifold was generated, it was than allocated to this structure the features of the original structure, and a unique arrow of time. Therefore, "the beginning of time" is only "the beginning of time" of this Three dimensional space, which serve as part of infinite spaces, embedded in one another, flattening each other via areas of extremum curvatures. In addition, our space itself serves as a generator for other spaces, with a distinct arrow and dimensions of their own.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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